

USE OF NATIONAL AND ACTIVITY GAMES IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION

Israilov Shoolim Shoakramovich

Senior teacher. Department of Theory and Methodology of Tennis,
Badminton, Table Tennis. Uzbekistan State
University of Physical Education and Sports. Tashkent. Uzbekistan

ANNOTATION

In the article, in order to ensure the implementation of measures related to the development of national and action games in our country today, it is more effective to teach the elements of national and folk games to students of higher education institutions. and methods of teaching folk games are discussed.

***Key words:** National and action games, game elements, body structure, stature, action games, introductory exercises, chillak, team, opponent's side, referee.*

Introduction

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, a rational system of personnel training is of great importance for the development of physical culture and sports. Therefore, the goals and objectives of physical culture in our republic are implemented based on the decisions of the government and the republican state committee for physical culture and sports. The goal of the physical culture implemented in the republic is to prepare a healthy, mentally fresh and creative person for life. This goal is a necessary task for all institutions and organizations engaged in physical culture in the Republic. Everyone should understand the necessity of physical culture and sports in order to educate himself physically and diligently build his health based on a certain system of physical training.

Methodology

Comprehensive development of the physical abilities of our people's children is carried out in the process of physical culture, which is an integral part of education. The purpose of physical culture is the process of making society healthy, cheerful, physically developed in all aspects, ready for work and protection of the Motherland. The essence of the need to teach and engage in national games with students in physical education classes in the higher education system is explained through an analytical method.

Data Collection and Analysis

There is no sport in nature that does not use the elements of national action games. The role of active games in strengthening the health of school children and educating young athletes is incomparable. The proof of this is that the standard and normative (limited) physical exercises (walking, running, hanging, pulling, bending legs and arms, bending, etc.) used during classes or training sessions are mostly in some cases, it extinguishes children's interest and lowers their mood. Most of the time, such trainings are not productive. According to the opinion of many experts, active games are recognized as a very effective tool for strengthening health and developing physical qualities. In order for students to succeed in classes aimed at acquiring movement skills, it is necessary to take into account the age characteristics of children in every way. The selection of national and movement games for training the qualities of movement is carried out taking into account the age. It is characteristic that dexterity, quickness, precision of movement and coordination occur in students of junior school age. The main questions of education and the formation of the physiological basis of conditioned reflexes and movement skills in children are now deeply studied and form the basis of physical education and sports. Based on the above, collecting national and action games, dividing them into categories, and increasing the quality and intensity of physical education classes is an important tool for raising children's interest. Therefore, their study is one of the urgent issues of the day. In the process of physical culture, the following main tasks are solved:

- a) strengthening health, training the body and increasing the level of physical development and work capacity;
- b) acquisition of skills and abilities necessary for life, including those of a practical nature;
- c) education of a person's moral and willful qualities;
- g) increase physical quality (speed, strength, dexterity, endurance);
- d) mastering the technique of performing a special sports exercise.

The task of the teacher as an organizer and educator is very responsible when conducting active games. It is important to pay special attention to the methodological consistency of the materials studied in the lesson, as well as in the process of conducting various games. Because consistency allows, firstly, to correctly solve the educational and educational tasks of the lesson, secondly, to achieve a complete passage of the lesson materials, and thirdly, to perform each exercise in a certain way throughout the lesson.

One of the important features of the physical education lesson is the efficient use of time. This event allows you to pass the lesson effectively. The teacher should use all opportunities for active participation of students in the lesson, as well as ensure that the tasks given to all students are the same. This can be achieved by clearly allocating time for each game and each participant. If the number of players is too large, it is necessary to form several groups or teams, to reduce the time set for completing the task. In order not to allow the game to be divided, it is necessary to prepare well for it, prepare the place of the game and the necessary equipment in advance.

Of course, weather conditions should be taken into account when planning action games according to the seasons of the school year. However, when the weather is good, games such as "Chillak", "Aq tosh", "Kaziq" are planned, but if necessary, they can be held inside the building instead. It is also necessary to specify the games (Usmonkho'jayev, 1992).

Result and Discussion

At the same time, collecting the national and dynamic games of the Uzbek people and implementing them in life, using them wisely, is an important task of both theoretical and practical importance. This task also placed a great responsibility on the physical culture that educates the young generation to be healthy and well-rounded. National movement games have their own characteristics because they are conducted mainly in the preparatory and final parts of physical education classes, because movement games are an auxiliary tool and focus on mastering one or another goal by preparing the body of pupils and students. Sometimes there may not be conditions in schools for the physical education program, but it is necessary to perform the tasks specified in the program. That's when using non-standard methods, i.e. elements of national action games, will give good results. Often, in rural conditions, due to the lack of equipment and the lack of a sports hall in rural conditions, if people use outdoor games, the purpose of the lesson will be partially fulfilled. National and movement games are complex activities consisting of emotional movements of this type. This activity is performed under the conditions and situations that suddenly change based on the established rules.

Conclusion

National and movement games differ from other physical exercises in the features of organizing and managing the activities of the participants. During the game, there is a need to act in suddenly changing situations and to solve movement tasks in a short period of time, showing physical qualities such as quickness and agility. It strengthens movement skills. During the game, children's activities are organized on the basis of figurative, plot or game tasks and arouse positive emotions with enthusiasm and long-term performance. This, in turn, strengthens their effect on the body, helps to develop physical qualities.

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